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“CHANGE YOUR STRATEGY” DEMAND OF TRACTOR INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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Abstract

Country witnessed below normal monsoon in few parts especially in south west areas but surprisingly it did not have much impact on tractor sales (domestic). Domestic tractor sales grew at 20% in 2013-14 & are likely to grow at 15% in 2014-15. Increase in Volume sales of tractors in domestic market from 5.26 lacks in 2012-13 to 6.34 lacks in 2013-14 reflects the brighter aspect of this industry in years to come.

Shift from single purpose tool to multipurpose tool for transportation & harvesting, Narega plan leading to acute shortage of labour in farm sector, demand of the sector for higher mechanization and frequent upward revision of Minimum support price of various crops are few factors contributing & pointing towards a flourishing industry.

However, a critical analysis of this industry over the years has clearly reflected a paradigm shift in its nature since pre- liberalization. Nature of the industry is again likely to change gradually in coming years. Industry participants must change their strategy to cope up with the challenges in order to survive and grow at a reasonable rate.

Present study is an attempt to critically examine the changing nature of tractor industry in India & outline the possible changes in existing strategy that the industry participants may consider to survive & grow.

Key words: *Multipurpose Tool, Minimum Support Price*

Introduction:-

Since independence in 1947, many efforts were put in by Government through its five year plans to achieve increased level of Agricultural & rural mechanization. Route preferred by local industrialists was joint ventures & technical tie ups with international giants in tractor manufacturing supported by government support. Efforts put in were commendable but growth rate achieved was slow in first three decades. Tractor production was around 14 lacks units per year.

It was after the economic reforms in 1991 that a remarkable change in pace was witnessed with around 27 lacks units per year in late 1990's. India surpassed US in early 2000 to become largest producer of tractors in the world.

History of pace of tractor industry in India can be summarised in given table:-

Year	Market characteristic	features	players	Production rise & total use
1947-60	Import market	Domestic requirement was met by imports	Imported	with around 8500 tractors in use in 1947 to 37000 in use in 1960
1961-80	Indigenou s production started in 1961	Concentration on indigenous production to meet the growth of agricultural mechanization generated by five year plans	5 local manufacturers (Eicher, Gujarat Tractors, TAFE, Escorts & M&M)	Production rose from 880 in 1961 to 5000 in 1965 & to 25000 in 1970. Total use rose from 37000 in 1960 to 1.46 lacks in 1970
1981-90	Importer to exporter	Achieved the exporter status during the period	Many more players entered like (HMT, Kirloskar, harsha, pittie,auto tractors, Haryana tractors, united auto, Asian tractors, VST Tillers) but few survived the tough competition.	Production rose from 75000 in 1985 to around 1.4 lacks in 1990 with total use of 1.2 million tractors.
1991-2000	Transitio n to world leader	Became world leader with around 26% of world production	LPG reforms in 1991 made its impact. Era was marked with India's transition to become world leader. Five more players entered(Bajaj tempo, new Holland, L& T JV with John deree, greeves ltd jv with Italian company deutz.)	Annual production reached all time high to 2.55 lacks units in 1997 with a forecast of 3 lacs units in 2000
2001-14	Challenge of saturatio n	Market showed symptoms of saturation in traditional market during the period.	Pareto's principle works here too. Five companies account for 80% of market share with 40% in the hand of M&M (M&M, Tafe, escorts, sonalika, john deree)	Production was 6,34 lacs units in 2013-14 & forecasted to be more or less same in 2014-15

Changing scenario:-

Tractor market has taken a leap due to the changing environmental factors. Those are the gone days when companies could sell their tractors on advance payment to their dealers & dealers could in turn sell it to farmers with long lead time. There is a paradigm shift from sellers market to buyers market now. Cas market has now changed to credit/finance market.

Though few of the tractor companies have adapted themselves to the changing environmental factors, even then the below given table shows that the industry has reached or reaching fast towards stagnation. After witnessing CAGR in tractor industry of 8.31% ,GDP Growth of 5.15% and agriculture growth rate of 2.20% in past two decades, the industry is witnessing a declining trend & is likely continue with the same trend in coming years.

Period		Domestic sales	Production	Export
89-90	97-98	8.3	9.2	41.3
98-99	03-04	-7.5	- 7.7	34.0
04-05	09-10	10.5	11.0	19.0
10-11	13-14	9.3	10.0	18.8
1989	2014	4.2	4.1	32.5

Monthly abstracts of stats, CSO

Factors driving the tractors demand:

Though tractors are meant for executing farm related functions but it has multiple uses in India ranging from transportation, goods carrier, industrial application etc. Hence In India Demand of tractors are not only driven by Agriculture but also driven by its multiple uses.

Various factors & it’s likely impact on tractor demand has been shown in following table:-

S.N	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Impact on demand
01	Agriculture production	Farmers purchasing capacity	Positive
02	Govt.procurement price	Agriculture production	Positive
03	Monsoon& net sown area	Agriculture production	Positive
04	Credit/Easy finance	Farmers purchase capacity	Positive
05	Refinance scheme by NABARD/RBI	Bank’s Loan sanctioning capacity	Positive
06	Scientific & innovative farming	Agriculture Production	Positive
07	Innovation in uses	Use value	positive

Compiled by the author

Though the domestic sales increased by 7% year of year in Sept 2014, after ding for two consecutive terms, over all below normal rainfall at 12% below the long period average may cause the tractor sales to skid in 2014-15 due to monsoon slippage (Crisil research 2014). Strategy adopted by the tractor industry seems to be over dependent on the balanced monsoon. & therefore demands a change in the existing strategy.

Objective of the study:-

The present study is an attempt to address the above question with following objectives:-

- Nature of tractor industry in India
- Challenges being faced by the players
- Existing strategy being practised by the key player
- Strategy change- A demand of the Industry.

Methodology & work organization:-

The nature of objectives chosen for the present study compels the study to be descriptive & exploratory which contributes to discover ideas & insights. The present study is based on secondary data taken out from various sources like articles published in journals, books, reports of reputed agencies, financial statements of Tractor Companies.

The present study has been organized in four heads as follows. In first head Tractor Industry has been analysed in macro context along with its future in coming years under the heading “ “ ”. It is followed by “Increased Competition & its impact on profitability “. Third section gives a brief overview of role and impact of celebrities under the head “Effect of celebrities and brand endorsers on the Advertising budget”. The fourth section concludes the secondary data and other interpretations.

Tractor marketing & challenges:-

Various challenges being faced by the tractor industry players can be tabulated:-

S.N	Challenge group	particulars
01	Buyers purchasing power	Increase in demand, higher expectation on comfort level, fuel economy, latest technology, longer life, new models & higher resale value
02	New technical regulations	New emission norms, EURO/3/US Tier-3, homologation test facilities, engine performance improvement, dedicated testing cells.
03	New product development	Higher engine performance, testing techniques, reduced lead time, fast prototyping
04	New safety regulation	Latest software tools, NVH Center of excellence, specialized test tracks, crash testing, ROPS Testing
05	Application of electronics	Application of Auto cruise system 7 GPS to help farmers
06	Alternate energy	Tractor development & Alternate energy source development are interdependent & poses a challenge
07	Testing networks	Establishment of NATRIP Centres
08	Export potential	Testing under different climatic conditions, testing and certification standardization etc

Automotive mission plan 2006-16 categorised the major challenges in three heads viz

- Sustaining the growth rate
- Innovation need
- Increasing the global share.

Above challenges in the tractor industry in India again calls for a change in Strategy.

Findings & Recommendation:-

In the changing scenario described above, some of the strategies that can be adopted by tractor industry players are:-

- To keep wide range of tractors
- Adoption of Aggressive marketing strategy
- Extension of finance scheme/increase of repayment tenure
- Reschedulement of loan for defaulters
- Adoption of promotional strategy with increased emphasis on price discounts & gift schemes to the farmers
- Shift to import of second hand tractors could be one of the strategy change. In develop countries, tractors are generally scrapped only after twoowth @8% & there are years of use. Government also in 2001 after WTO Treaty, rationalized import duty structure on 2nd hand tractors from 67% to around 62.8%. This could be another option for the companies to import and sell it to the same target market at a very competitive price

However these measures would be a short term measures. Companies must think in terms of long term measures.

Companies must develop a supply base in long run marked by lower costs, attaining economies of scale, initiating measures for developing technical & human capabilities, removing infrastructural imbalances, taking measures to augment domestic demand and exploiting the international market.

It can therefore be recommended that achievement of critical mass to make country more competitive and profitable for investments would be the key to success in long run. Companies must address following challenges in long run to sustain:-

- Manufacturing competitiveness

- Flow of technology
- Demand & brand building
- Infrastructural issues
- International business
- Environmental & safety standards

Improvement in manufacturing competitiveness would be the key to success. 17% Share of manufacturing in India's GDP in comparison to 35% of GDP in developed countries reflect a negative picture.. This would not only require a strategy change by companies but also a high degree of support from the government.

Some support that would be required from the government are

- ✓ Reducing the high import duty on raw materials along with reduction of incidence of indirect cash.
- ✓ Measures to obtain optimum levels of operation to bring operational efficiency.
- ✓ Measures to lower the transaction costs..
- ✓ Measures to improve labour productivity & lowering the cost of capital.

Companies on the other hand must take following measures towards its strategies in order to sustain and grow.:-

- ✓ More priority and investment in Technology and Research & Development.
- ✓ Continuous programs for skill development & education.
- ✓ To bring the culture of brench marking against the best in industry
- ✓ By adopting the best manufacturing practices & techniques.
- ✓ By delivering globally approved quality levels.

Conclusion:-

The paper was an attempt to review the past, present & future of the Indian tractor industry. It has been found that tractor demand is influenced by many factors not in line with developed European countries.

Primary demand comes out of agricultural growth and the secondary demand comes from multiple uses of tractors. Indian tractor industry relatively amateur by world standards has witnessed a spectacular growth of expansion during last many decades barring few exceptions in few years due to specific reasons. Industry is however witnessing a stagnation phase because of its overdependence on agriculture and monsoon. he farmer's choice, of tractor size, is a compromise, between, the utility of the tractor, for multiple uses, including, haulage and, its price.

Industry also needs support from the government in terms of multiple incentives especially for indigenou Research & development like government has done by reducing import dutu on 2nd hand tractors from 67% to 57%. This will help in bringing focus on R&D in tractors, in India. This will also lead to higher mechanization which in turn increase the tractor demand thus helping the tractor industry as a whole.

If Industry players adapt to the suggested recommendation then the Industry will probably expand at an annual growth of 8% with probability of an even distribution of market share among the major players in the industry. Market is most likely to witness mergers/acquisitions & bilateral resource sharing arrangements in years to come.

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